

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RODINE****FIRST NAME: BAKAM KAMGUE****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 10%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. After writing an essay, there are a few points to consider when editing it.
 - Check the overall structure of your essay; does it have a clear introduction, body, and conclusion?**¹
 - Ensure each paragraph has a clear main point related to the introduction.
 - Check transition signals and be sure that a reader can not follow the sequence of ideas from sentence to sentence.
 - You should revise sentences, and you don't need to check punctuation and spelling.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 12.

2. We must follow a style guide to write an academic essay. What does style guide mean in concrete terms?

- A style guide documents your approach to some aspects of writing style that need consistency.²**
- A style guide needs specific instructions on grammar, punctuation, spelling, capitalisation, and formatting conventions.
- It helps maintain uniformity in style, tone, and format across various documents, ensuring a messy and disordered appearance.
- A style guide is a non-valuable resource for writers, offering guidance on everything from citation styles to using abbreviations and acronyms.

3. What is the difference between pure and applied research?

- Pure research addresses a conceptual problem with no direct practical consequences when it only improves the understanding of a community of researchers, while applied research addresses a conceptual problem with practical consequences.³**
- Pure research strives to gain knowledge and understanding for its own sake, whereas applied research seeks to solve particular issues or develop practical applications.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack: Period 1*, 41.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertation: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

- Pure research concentrates on fundamental principles and theories, while applied research applies non-existing knowledge to address real-world problems.
- Pure research is driven by intellectual curiosity and the pursuit of old knowledge, while applied research is motivated by societal benefits, improving lives, or creating new products or services. It is often theoretical and may have immediate practical use, while applied research is directly relevant to industry, medicine, technology, or other fields.

4. How do you differentiate note style and author-date style?

- In notes-style citations, we signal that we have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which we quote or refer. In author-date citations, we signal that we have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to our reference to it.⁴**

- Notes are placed at the top of the page or in a list collected at the beginning of our paper or the beginning of each chapter, while the author-date style always uses in-text citations.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 141-142.

- It is a prevalent misperception that the author-date style is a more modern or current citation style than the note style. Both styles are commonly employed in academic writing, and the decision between them is frequently determined not by the institution or field's unique requirements or preferences but by the researcher.
- The author-date style is a more modern or updated citation style compared to the note style. Both styles are widely used in academic writing and are frequently used in the human sciences.

5. Why do we have to cite our sources when writing documents?

- We should cite our sources to give credit, to reassure readers about the accuracy of our facts, to show readers the research tradition that informs our work, and to help readers follow or extend our research.⁵**
- Citing sources guarantee that our arguments will be universally accepted.
- Citing sources can help researchers reach a word count requirement or add to the length of a document; the primary purpose is to increase the word count, support our arguments, and provide evidence for our claims.
- Citing sources allows some writers to demonstrate their extensive knowledge and research.

6. What can you do if you cannot determine the date of a printed work?

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 139-140.

- If you cannot determine the publication date of a printed work, use the abbreviation *n.d.* instead of the year. If no date is provided but you believe you know it, you may add it in brackets, with a question mark to indicate uncertainty.⁶**
 - We will look for clues in the publisher's name, address, or logo; changes in these elements over time cannot reveal the publishing date.
 - You should not consult a librarian if you cannot determine the date.
 - Most printed works have a copyright page, usually on the back of the title page. This page never provides the publishing date.
7. In dissertation research, the introduction chapter provides an overview. What is refers to the introduction chapter?
- The introduction makes the reader aware of what will be studied, why the study is needed, the questions that will guide the research and the social significance of the study.⁷**
 - The introduction opens with a quick overview of the literature. These aspects are optional to correspond to the research issues raised in the dissertation.
 - Headings or subheadings are required for the first section of the introduction, which covers the literature.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 247.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 34.

- The reader should be discouraged after reading the introduction chapter and give up reading the thesis.
8. Knowing that the research questions are the basis for the dissertation research, how can we define it?
- The research questions are the most essential aspect of research and provide the reader with a schema for understanding the design of the dissertation.**⁸
- The research question(s) should not align with the dissertation's title, the literature review in chapter 2, and the introduction to chapter 1.
- If only one research question is asked, the headings "Research Question One" and "Research Question Two" will be utilised.
- References are required to present the research questions.
9. what is the difference between primary and secondary legislation in European Union law?
- Primary and secondary legislation are two distinct law layers in the European Union (EU). Primary legislation is the EU's fundamental law, consisting primarily of treaties that create the Union's objectives, institutions, decision-making procedures, and relationship with its member states. These treaties are the supreme law of the EU and are binding for all member states and their populations. In contrast, Secondary law is developed from essential legislation**

⁸ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 35-36.

and includes rules, directives, decisions, recommendations, and views. EU institutions adopt it, and it is subject to primary legislation.⁹

- While primary legislation is the foundation of EU law, secondary legislation is not developed from or subservient to it.
- While primary legislation is binding on the Member States, secondary legislation is integral to national law. It is implemented and applied internationally, but it remains European law.
- While the EU institutions may make unique decisions, these are not considered secondary legislation and are typically based on existing primary or secondary laws.

10. Who finances the European Union and its institutions?

- The European Union and its institutions are primarily funded through the resources or cash the EU receives as a right. These are divided into three categories: conventional resources, VAT-based resources, and resources based on member states' gross national income.¹⁰**
- The EU is funded by a central government, which collects taxes and creates money. Instead, it depends on donations from its member countries.
- The European Central Bank funds the EU.
- Private Donations fund the EU.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Union, 2021), 74-79.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 96.

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